

Impact of post-fibrinolytic angioplasty on mortality and complications

Impacto de la angioplastia post-fibrinolítica en la mortalidad y las complicaciones

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Abstract

Ischemic heart disease (IHD) is the leading cause of death and disability worldwide, posing a significant public health concern regarding the quality of life and health-associated financial burden. Considering the impact of IHD in all areas, proper management has become the principal interest of many associations. While international guidelines recommend implementing a watchful strategy after thrombolysis, emerging evidence might show otherwise. Some authors have suggested to perform an early percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) after thrombolysis to further increase the benefits of the revascularization therapy. This alternative has been termed early routine post-thrombolysis PCI (ER-PCI). Several researchers have compared it against current recommendations to find whether it is truly advantageous. This review aims to analyze the evidence regarding the benefits of ER-PCI in contrast to current strategies, considering mortality, complications, and reinfarction as primary endpoints for comparison.

Keywords: Ischemic heart disease, early routine percutaneous coronary intervention, cardiovascular disease, revascularization therapy, thrombolysis.

Resumen

La cardiopatía isquémica (CI) es la principal causa de muerte y discapacidad en todo el mundo, y representa un importante problema de salud pública por su impacto en la calidad de vida y la carga económica asociada. Teniendo en cuenta la repercusión de la CI en todos estos ámbitos, su adecuado manejo se ha convertido en el principal foco de interés de múltiples asociaciones. Aunque las guías internacionales recomiendan una estrategia de observación vigilante tras la trombólisis, nueva evidencia podría señalar lo contrario. Algunos autores han propuesto realizar una intervención coronaria percutánea (ICP) precoz tras la trombólisis para potenciar aún más los beneficios de la terapia de reperfusión. Esta alternativa se ha denominado ICP rutinaria precoz post-trombólisis (ER-PCI, por sus siglas en inglés). Varios investigadores la han comparado con las recomendaciones actuales para determinar si realmente aporta ventajas. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo analizar la evidencia acerca de los beneficios de la ER-PCI en comparación con las estrategias actuales, considerando la mortalidad, las complicaciones y el reinfarto como criterios de valoración principales.

Palabras clave: cardiopatía isquémica, intervención coronaria percutánea rutinaria precoz, enfermedad cardiovascular, terapia de revascularización, trombólisis.

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of global mortality and a major contributor to disability. The prevalence of CVD nearly doubled between 1990 and 2019, going from 271 million to 523 million. Likewise, CVD-associated deaths increased from 12.1 million to 18.6 million¹. The exponential growth of CVD can be explained through a variety of possibilities. Firstly, the increased prevalence of metabolic conditions like diabetes mellitus (DM) and dyslipidemia have been directly linked to CVD. Likewise, the prevalence of obesity has grown in parallel to that of CVD, and behavioral and environmental risk factors like physical inactivity and unhealthy dietary habits are more prevalent than 30 years ago². Notably, ischemic heart disease (IHD) is the most relevant CVD in terms of mortality, morbidity, and disability. As a result, there is significant interest in the science community to decrease the incidence of IHD through preventive measures³.

However, despite implementing proper standardized prevention protocols, IHD remains a paramount public health concern⁴. Therefore, the most accurate approach to decrease the socioeconomic impact of IHD and the worsening quality of life of patients is optimal treatment^{5,6}. IHD has several forms of presentation, but ST-elevation segment myocardial infarction (STEMI) is the most severe and most tightly associated with complications and mortality⁷. International protocols have stated that timely revascularization—either medical or surgical—is the gold standard for the management of STEMI, reducing postinfarction morbidity and complications to nearly zero⁸.

Since not every healthcare facility can perform a PCI, especially rural institutions, fibrinolysis remains a feasible alternative when recommended door-to-balloon time thresholds cannot be met^{9,10}. While international guidelines recommend implementing a watchful strategy after thrombolysis, emerging evidence might show otherwise. Some authors have suggested to perform an early PCI after thrombolysis to further increase the benefits of the revascularization therapy¹¹. This alternative has been termed early routine post-thrombolysis PCI (ER-PCI). Several researchers have compared it against current recommendations to find whether it is truly advantageous¹². This review aims to analyze the evidence regarding the benefits of ER-PCI in contrast to current strategies, considering mortality, complications, and reinfarction as primary endpoints for comparison.

POST-FIBRINOLYTIC ANGIOPLASTY: WHERE ARE WE STANDING?

It is widely accepted that the optimal approach to treat STEMI is reperfusion, either in the form of PCI or fibrinolytic therapy. The treatment choice often depends solely on the availability of transportation to the nearest PCI center and the time separation between both locations¹³. Irrespective of treatment choice, avoiding time delays is the most crucial variable in reducing total ischemia time¹⁴. A substantial number of institutes cannot perform timely PCI. Moreover, it is also impossible for some of these facilities to transport their patients to a PCI center within recommended time limitations. The latter is especially true in rural areas and developing countries, resulting in many patients being treated through thrombolytic therapy¹⁵.

Fibrinolytic therapy has proven to be an effective approach to treat STEMI, but it has been historically outperformed by PCI in terms of negative and positive outcomes. A systematic review analyzed 23 randomized trials comparing the effectiveness of PCI and fibrinolytic therapy. The proportion of patients was distributed symmetrically, with 50.03% of the patients treated through PCI and the other half with fibrinolytic therapy. It was demonstrated that PCI significantly reduced the overall short-term mortality, independent of the thrombolytic agent employed¹⁶. Moreover, it has been reported that patients receiving fibrinolytic therapy have an increased risk of bleeding compared to those receiving PCI. Moderate to severe bleeding has been reported as a result of fibrinolytic therapy; furthermore, African Americans seem to have a significantly higher risk of bleeding than Caucasians¹⁷.

Recent observational investigations have stated that differences in mortality between PCI and fibrinolytic therapy are negligible when they are performed early. Likewise, the most expedited recommendation from these researchers is to perform the most readily available revascularization alternative to improve clinical outcomes¹⁸. However, the methodology and sampling of the latter studies lack the statistical power to represent the worldwide population. Strong evidence has shown that PCI significantly reduces short-term mortality, stroke incidence and reinfarction rates, compared to fibrinolysis^{19,20}. Consequently, there is growing interest in optimizing fibrinolysis through diverse methods and performing an immediate angioplasty after successful thrombolysis has been extensively studied to address this problem. The main limitation to performing a PCI is time; presumably, thrombolysis can buy the time needed to provide the patient with the needed PCI to obtain all its benefits²¹.

The concept of performing a PCI after thrombolytic therapy was termed facilitated PCI (FPCI). Initially, FPCI was proposed as an alternative to patients receiving only fibrinolytic therapy. It was hypothesized that providing an

open artery on arrival at the catheterization laboratory would logistically facilitate the procedure and provide pharmacologic treatment synergistic with the procedure itself²¹. Observational studies at the time showed compelling results. Firstly, Brodie et al.²² showed that patients with TIMI (Thrombolysis in Myocardial Infarction) 2-3 flow on initial angiography had better procedural results, fewer complications, smaller infarct size, shorter total ischemia time and lower in-hospital mortality compared to patients with TIMI 0-1 flow. Similarly, Stone et al.²³ found that patients with TIMI 3 flow on arrival had better in-hospital outcomes and survival at six months. Likewise, recovery of left ventricular function and late cardiac survival rates were improved in the FPCI group.

However, other trials have failed to show similar improvement in clinical outcomes and also stated that major hemorrhagic events were significantly more frequent in the FPCI group²⁴. Moreover, a systematic review analyzed nearly 30 articles assessing FPCI. At the time, the available evidence was inadequate to recommend routine transfer of patients for immediate or ER-PCI after successful thrombolysis. This conclusion persisted for a significant time, considering the divergent outcomes and their inconsistency regarding positive outcomes^{25,26}. The controversial evidence regarding FPCI might be the product of the lack of synergy between fibrinolytic therapy and PCI at the moment without the improvements of drug-eluting stents and platelet glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitors (PGI)²¹.

Several trials have consistently demonstrated that implementing fibrinolytic therapy, even with half dosing, provides better TIMI flow at the time of angiography at the catheterization laboratory. However, old trials failed to report significant differences in infarct size, left ventricular function, and clinical outcomes between the primary PCI group and the FPCI group^{11,27}. Furthermore, the impact of the up-front implementation of PGIs was also assessed. The ON-TIME trial demonstrated that patients treated with tirofiban prior to catheterization were significantly more likely to have TIMI 2-3 flow at the initial angiography. Nonetheless, there were no differences in clinical outcomes at one year²⁸. Conversely, a meta-analysis reported that patients treated with up-front abciximab had a higher frequency of TIMI 2-3 flow at the initial angiography, mildly related to improvements in clinical outcomes²⁹.

More recent studies have evaluated more variables in order to increase the accuracy of the conclusions. Cantor et al.³⁰ analyzed the role and optimal timing of ER-PCI, which had not been established at the time. All patients received aspirin, tenecteplase, heparin or enoxaparin; concomitantly, clopidogrel was recommended, and most patients received it. Patients undergoing ER-PCI showed significantly less risk of reinfarction, recurrent ischemia, new or worsening heart failure, and death within 30 days (relative risk (RR): 0.64; 95% CI, 0.47-0.87). In conclusion, transfer for ER-PCI within 6 hours after fibrinolysis

was associated with fewer complications and better outcomes than the standard treatment.

Similarly, D'Souza et al.³¹ analyzed the outcomes of patients receiving ER-PCI over standard ischemia-guided PCI recommended by international protocols. The meta-analysis concluded that when primary PCI is not feasible, ER-PCI within 24 hours of thrombolysis is a safe and easily achievable strategy with significantly better outcomes than ischemia-guided PCI. ER-PCI resulted in less recurrence of ischemia and reinfarction at no increased risk of major hemorrhage. Likewise, Zhang et al.³² performed another meta-analysis on ER-PCI efficacy and safety within 24 hours of thrombolysis. Analyses showed that the ER-PCI group had significantly less risk of mortality, reinfarction and recurrence of ischemia (RR: 0.52, 95% CI, 0.42-0.65). As the previous study, Zhang et al.³² concluded that the benefits of ER-PCI were achieved at no greater risk of major hemorrhage.

Recent and higher-quality researches have indisputably stated the benefits of ER-PCI, which is partly due to newer pharmacoinvasive strategies and drug-eluting stents³³. More importantly, recent investigations have demonstrated the non-inferiority of ER-PCI in contrast to primary PCI, a statement that could significantly change current paradigms in coronary care. The WEST study compared the primary endpoint of death, reinfarction, congestive heart failure, and other major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) in patients receiving primary PCI and ER-PCI. Analyses showed no significant difference between the groups, suggesting that both procedures are equally beneficial. However, these observations should be taken with caution due to the low population of the trial³⁴. The ongoing GRACIA-4 trial is expected to compare the clinical efficacy of these two procedures as a randomized, multicentre, open-label clinical trial with at least 1400 patients (NCT02268669).

The most recent review comparing the effectiveness of ER-PCI and primary PCI reported that according to real-world data, no significant differences were found in the in-hospital outcomes between patients with STEMI who received primary PCI or ER-PCI³⁵. The authors suggest that the overall equal performance between these two procedures relies partly on decision-making and time management. Patients that received ER-PCI had a shorter first medical contact time, shorter medical contact to reperfusion time, and less total ischemic time until reperfusion, which is the main goal in the overall management of IHD³⁵. Similarly, the long-term follow-up of the TRANSFER-AMI study reported that patients that received ER-PCI showed no statistically significant differences in MACE after almost eight years of follow-up compared to the group treated with primary PCI³⁶.

In light of the emerging evidence, ER-PCI has been separated into two groups; FPCI, when the interval between fibrinolysis and PCI is less than 2 hours and pharmacoinvasive approach, when an intentionally lon-

References

ger fibrinolysis to PCI interval is implemented, between 2 and 24 hours³⁷. Considering this division, several trials have found that FPCI is consistently inferior compared to primary PCI³⁸. However, another group of trials have consistently demonstrated that the pharmacoinvasive approach is far superior to fibrinolytic therapy and at least equally beneficial compared to primary PCI when substantial time delays are present^{39,40}. A recent meta-analysis demonstrated that the pharmacoinvasive approach is safer and more effective than FPCI and fibrinolytic therapy alone. However, timely primary PCI remains the preferred option in patients that can be readily approached by that procedure⁴¹.

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Conclusions

IHD is the leading cause of death and disability worldwide, posing a significant public health concern regarding the quality of life and health-associated financial burden. Considering the impact of IHD in all areas, proper management has become the principal interest of many associations. International protocols have been standardized and widely applied worldwide, resulting in significantly better outcomes when recommendations are strictly enforced. However, as primary PCI is unavailable for a large proportion of the world's population, it has become necessary to understand alternative reperfusion strategies' relative efficacy and safety. In order to address this problem, the idea of ER-PCI has been put to the test. While early results were somewhat deficient, rapid optimization and implementation of new technologies and drugs allowed this idea to evolve appropriately. To date, FPCI and pharmacoinvasive approaches have enough evidence to recommend them as an alternative to primary PCI. Even international recommendations have agreed to consider this alternative in their guidelines. Further efforts are needed to optimize this alternative and answer pending questions concerning this procedure, but current evidence shows promising results.

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